

CONTENT AND COMPOSITION, FACTORS AND CRITERIA OF THE CONCEPT OF "SOCIAL CAPITAL"

Norgabilov Muzaffar Jumaevich

Philosophy Doctor (PhD)

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Abstract. *In this article, social capital is one of the most important factors in ensuring national unity. Social capital is a concept that expresses the nature of relations between members of society, their mutual cooperation and trust, and the degree of inclination to common social norms and values. At the same time, it is stated that this phenomenon with a complex composition is formed under the influence of a number of natural, historical, socio-economic, political, and spiritual factors and is measured using specific criteria.*

Keywords: *social capital, national unity, social relations, equal rights, spiritual and cultural life, moral values, nation, religion.*

Today, socio-economic, political, spiritual and cultural processes aimed at establishing New Uzbekistan are gaining momentum. In order for these processes to end with significant results, there must be a certain political program, of course. Such a program will be implemented on November 6, 2021 by Sh. It is well known that Mirziyoyev was announced at the inauguration ceremony. But there is another aspect of the matter. The implementation of any program of serious importance also requires the strengthening of national unity. Because if there is no unanimity, solidarity, and cooperation among the representatives of the nation, even the noblest goals will remain a dream. In this regard, the analysis of factors for strengthening national unity is of particular importance.

National unity means unanimity of representatives of the nation. This unanimity is formed on the basis of harmony of needs and interests, mutual trust and cooperation. National unity has always been an important factor in ensuring social stability and development of society. Therefore, the problems related to the determination of national unity have been widely studied by experts. For example, at the beginning of the last century, the French sociologist E. Durkheim carefully studied various aspects of this problem and put forward the theory of national solidarity [1]

However, by the last quarter of the 20th century, the issues of preserving national unity took on a new meaning. Because, on the one hand, the factors that undermine the integrity of social systems in the society of individuals have increased more and more. On the other hand, international socio-economic, political and cultural processes have become extremely complicated. In the situation that has arisen, the task of maintaining unity among the representatives of the nation is becoming more and more difficult. Therefore, this task is becoming one of the priority directions of the policy implemented by the states. It is for this reason that the head of state said: "Our focus will be on the further development of mutual friendship and solidarity in our society, ensuring equal rights for all citizens, regardless of nationality, religion and belief" [2].

The factors that serve to ensure and strengthen national unity are characterized by their diversity. Various economic, social, political, legal, spiritual and cultural factors are mentioned in this regard. All these comments are appropriate and reasonable, of course. But there is also a

powerful factor of social capital in ensuring national cohesion. Because it is social capital that serves to strengthen the socio-economic, political and spiritual foundations of national unity.

The concept of "social capital" was first used in the article of the English scientist L.J.Hanifan. The author used it to determine the level of solidarity in society and the standard of people's participation in social life. After that, this concept was not in scientific circulation for many years. The concept of "social capital" began to reappear in scientific sources only by the 60s of the last century. In particular, the American scientist J. Jacobs used this concept to express the importance of social relations [3]

Since the 80s of the last century, the concept of "social capital" has become one of the most discussed concepts of Western sociology. Its content and composition are systematically by P.Burde. It has been thoroughly revealed The scientist understands social capital as a set of social relations that can bring a certain benefit [4]. Later, his comments were published by sociologist D.Coleman and political scientist developed by R.Petnam[5]. They note that there is a set of social norms and moral values that are followed by all members of society. According to scientists, these norms and values allow establishing social cooperation on a community scale. For example, R.Petnam connects the concept of "social capital" with the characteristic features of social life (interaction, norms, trust), which he claims allows the subjects of economic activity in society to act effectively towards a common goal. The scientist claims that social capital plays a decisive role in ensuring economic well-being in society and in achieving the development of the socio-political sphere [6]

Even today, various theoretical conclusions regarding the content and structure of social capital are put forward. The important point is that despite the large number of such conclusions, it is extremely difficult to bring the opinions to a common denominator. Because one group of researchers interprets social capital as an important attribute of the whole society. In this case, social capital is analyzed as a concept that shows the proportionality of a person's behavior to norms generally recognized in society. The second group of researchers defines social capital as a concept that represents resources and social relations in a certain social group [7]

The third group of researchers imagines social capital as a set of characteristics unique to an individual. According to them, these characteristics are formed by the individual's membership in a certain social group. Therefore, the definitions given to the concept of "social capital" are also different due to the diversity of the researchers' theoretical and methodological position, and the many points of view. Moreover, in recent years, the analysis of the concept of "social capital" in the economic context has become a trend. However, the peculiarity of the issue is that social capital is a characteristic of society, an attribute related not only to its economic, but also to its political, social, spiritual and cultural life, so it is appropriate to research it in a socio-philosophical context [8]

In conclusion, social capital is one of the most important factors in ensuring national cohesion. Social capital is a concept that expresses the nature of relations between members of society, their mutual cooperation and trust, and the degree of inclination to common social norms and values. This complex phenomenon is formed under the influence of a number of natural, historical, socio-economic, political, and spiritual factors and is measured using specific criteria.

REFERENCES

1. Алиев И.Т. Психология ва педагогика. - Тошкент: Фан ва технология, 2012.

2. Ахлоқ // Ўзбекистон Миллий Энциклопедияси. Ж.1. - Тошкент: “Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси”, 2000.
3. Ахмедшаева М.А. Ҳозирги замон давлати ва ҳуқуқ назарияси муаммолари. - Тошкент: Тошкент Давлат юридик институти, 2006.
4. Баскакова И.В. Осенка социального капитала в различных странах // XIX Международная конференция “Культура, личность, общество в современном мире: методология, опыт эмпирического исследования”: сборник материалов конференции. - Екатеринбург, Уралский Федеральный университет, 2016.
5. Бойназаров Ф. Қадимги дунё тарихи. - Тошкент: Абдулла Қодирий номидаги халқ мероси нашриёти, 2004.
6. Бурде П. Сосолиогия политики.- Москва: Сосои-Логос, 1993.
7. Восстание рабов под руководством Спартака (74–71 гг. до н. е.) // [хттп://справочник.ру/история/восстание_рабов_под_руководством_спартака_74_71_гг_до_н_е/](http://справочник.ру/история/восстание_рабов_под_руководством_спартака_74_71_гг_до_н_е/).
8. Гаспаров М.Л. Занимательная Греция: Рассказы о древнегреческой культуре. - Москва: Новое литературное обозрение, 2000.
9. Y Kadirova, K Kadirova SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF PEDAGOGUE IN SOCIO-POLITICAL LIFE OF SOCIETY//Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. В3. – Pp. 417-421
10. Кадырова, Я. Б. YOSHLARDA FUKAROLIK MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH ORQALI VATANPARVARLIK VA BAYNALMINALLIK TUYG ‘ULARINI, RIVOJLANTIRISH/JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH. 2023/2/25.B-197-202
11. Kadirova, Y. B. (2023). TA’LIM JARAYONIDA O ‘QITISHNING INTEGRATIV TEXNOLOGIYALARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH VA AMALIYOTIDA QO ‘LLASH. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(10), 541-548.
12. Buvabaevna, K. Y., & named after Nizami, T. D. P. U. (2021). THE ROLE OF FAMILY AND EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN INCREASING THE CIVIL LITERACY OF STUDENTS. MODERN SCIENTIFIC CHALLENGES AND TRENDS, 140.
13. Қодирова, Х. Б. (2015). МИЛЛИЙ ЎЗЛИКНИ АНГЛАШ. *FORMATION A CULTURE OF INDEPENDENT THINKING IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS*, 86.
14. Kadirova, X. B. (2023). YOSHLARNINI MILLIY QADRIYATLAR RUHIDA TARBIYALASHDA OILALA VA MAHALLALARNING RO’LI. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(10), 549-554.
15. Buvabayevna, K. X. (2023). Yoshlarning Huquqiy Madaniyatni Shakillantirishda Ijtimoiy-Ma’naviy Muxitning Ta’siri. *O'zbekistonda Fanlararo Innovatsiyalar Va Ilmiy Tadqiqotlar Jurnal*, 2(19), 879-884.
16. Buvabaevna, K. H., & Medetovna, A. F. Development And Preservation Of Karakalpak Ethnic Culture. *Multidisciplinary Approaches in the Current Times*, 63.
17. Y Kadirova, S Komilova. THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL NETWORKS ON HUMAN CONSCIOUSNESS// Science and Innovation.2022 – Т. 1. – №. В8.- Pp.1360-1363
18. Kadirova Yakitjan Buvabaevna, Kadirova Khalima Buvabaevna. METHODOLOGICAL Basis Of Development Of Legal Immunity Of Students On The Basis Of A Subject-Ethical Approach. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*. 2022/12/23. Pp.6480-6487. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47750/pnr.2022.13.S09.771>